

All Things Work Together for Our Good

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Let us begin with a popular and insightful story! Once there was a famous king who had a wise minister who always looked at life with a positive attitude. For all that happens in life his constant reply would be “it is for good.” One day the king’s only son lost one of his fingers while playing with the knife. The minister on hearing the news told the king that “it is for good”. The king got enraged with this answer from the minister and immediately ordered the soldiers to put the minister into prison. And once again the reply of the minister was “it is for good.” After some days the king’s son went for hunting in the forest and to his bad luck, he was captured by the pagans who decided to offer him as a sacrifice to their deity. When they were about to slit his throat, they noticed that his finger was missing so they left him free. The king’s son reported the matter to the king that he was captured and released free because he missed his finger. The king remembered the words of the minister and brought him out from the prison and enquired why he said “it is for good” while he was put in prison? He said “if I was not put in prison, I would have accompanied the prince for hunting as usual and they would have sacrificed me instead of him.” This reply of the minister convinced the king that all things work together for good.

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God's Ways Are Different from Ours

This simple story narrated above serves as an eye opener for us to look at life with eyes of faith. The holy Bible too explains to us of the fact that all things work together for good. We see this from the book of Genesis to the book of Revelation. St. Augustine hails the original sin as 'blessed' because it brought forth the Savior to the rest of humanity, while as others consider it as a curse. Even when Joseph was sold by his own brothers to the Egyptians, he was convinced that it was not his brothers who sent him to Egypt but God, in order to preserve their lives during famine (cf. Gen 45:5). We can't understand the mighty plans of God with our bare eyes but only with the eyes filled with faith can we come to realize that everything happens for our good.

The more human beings suffer, the more God's mercy and love abounds. We see in the book of Job, how he was abandoned by God to dust but finally was restored to health and wealth in double. Our God is an awesome God, his ways are mysterious. If Jesus, the Only Son of God did not undergo passion and death, the realization of our salvation would be impossible. Thus, our God who is very loving brings beautiful things out of the things that seem to be hopeless and turns everything for our good.

This conviction is not limited to Bible alone. When we apply this fact to the historical events like natural calamities, accidents, diseases and so on, we come to understand that God has a purpose behind all these. And when we realize this great truth, we become open to God's workings and thus we will be able to find the hidden meaning in these catastrophes. I would like to bring to our attention the situation of a village affected by the Tsunami 2014. We know that the millions of people suffered the loss of dear ones, their property and their all the belongings. We know all is not lost when everything seems to be lost. They are only a new beginning towards something good, better or sometimes even for something that is for best. The village that I was talking about was in a poor state with no basic facilities and with no proper living conditions before tsunami.

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No one cared that such a village existed. But today, thanks to the generosity of so many generous souls, the village is transformed into a beautiful place with proper houses and all basic facilities. It is just an amazing thing to visit that village now. Though there were many losses, God had his own plan to make us convince that all things work together for good. God's ways are different from ours. And it is always for the better!

Through the Eyes of Faith

It is true at present the whole world is passing through a painful period due to COVID-19, which has jeopardized the whole world of its economy, human resources, environment and so on. It has brought about a huge faith crisis. We are drawn to ask questions like: Is still God in control of history? Or is he enjoying the human miseries? Does God care for us? etc. It is quite natural that we are induced to ask such questions but at the same time we should also see the good things that this time of crisis brings to us. This crisis that we are facing today is certainly not a work of God but clinging onto God we can certainly overcome this crisis. We do acknowledge that this problem has done unimaginable harm to humanity. It has caused mind-boggling suffering to all of us. It is terribly bad. Still I would like to point out a few things as to how this present crisis can be a way to transformation if only, we can see it through the eyes of faith:

- It can bring about oneness in the family. An opportunity to spend more time for one another, to care and express one's concern for the other members in the family.

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- It can turn the attention of the people from unwanted things like peer addictions, drugs, alcohol and make them to turn towards God.
- It can inspire the rich people to contribute to the needs of the poor.
- The distinction between the rich and poor are removed and brought into a balance.
- The environment has been brought into a peaceful atmosphere.
- The value of human life is emphasized, and a time to put into practice what one has been taught to value in life more.
- A time to retreat oneself from where one has fallen from the commitment in life.
- A time to reflect and contribute the capacity to think creatively and pen down in words the insights received.

“We know that all things work together for good for those who love God and who are called according to his purpose” (Rom 8:28).

Conclusion

Besides these, there can be many other ways how this corona virus period brings a positive outlook to glance through the eyes of faith. Every tragedy in life shakes our faith, brings confusion, pain and turmoil and uncontrollable tears but for a Christian who passes through these catastrophes with the eyes of faith, God turns everything for our good. St. Paul in his letter to the Romans says “we know that all things work together for good for those who love God and who are called according to his purpose” (Rom 8:28). Here St. Paul puts a condition that it is only for those who love God, God turns everything for good. As convinced Christians, we know that our God does not wait for our love. His love and compassion cannot be explored by us, his creatures. God is with us in this time of

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suffering and misery and he, for sure, will turn everything for our good. Let us have the patience to see all things work together for our good.

